

Patterns of WhatsApp usage and its Impact on Graduate Level Students of Rural Vaijapur Dist. Aurangabad (MS)

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Abstract:- WhatsApp is becoming useful to the any citizens, employees and businessman. Its popularity is gradually increasing in society and students are no exception. In this paper we try to understand the patterns of whatsapp usage and its impact on the personality development and overall behaviour of the graduate level students. The data has been collected from 310 respondents of senior college students with structured questionnaire. The findings shows that, 91.29 % respondents are using WhatsApp. 60.32 % of the respondents say that social relations have become closer because of WhatsApp 87.09% of the respondents say that WhatsApp keeps them informed about world affairs. 61.29% of the respondents said that the amount of books, newspaper reading and watching TV has decreased due to mobile phones. 61.93% respondents said they are addicted by WhatsApp.

Keywords:- Personality, Social Relation, Addiction, Irritability, Conflict.

I. INTRODUCTION

WhatsApp is one of the most important social media like, other social media in modern society. It is becoming useful to the any citizens, employees and businessman. Because people are using it for messaging, video calling, advertisement of products and services and communication information support etc. Hence its popularity is gradually increasing in society and students are no exception. So we try to understand the patterns of whatsapp usage and its impact on the personality development and overall behaviour of the graduate level students of rural Vijapur.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

“Previously, only friends and lovers tend to possess robust relationships with intimate conversations but now WhatsApp has created a way of belongingness, intimate conversations, sharing and exchanging information (Kumar,

Sharma 2016)¹. It has perceived the benefits to maintaining friendship and keeping in touch with friends (Farhan and Varghese 2018)². It is useful to make immediate communication and coordination among users (Temirlan Jailobaev, and et al. 2012)³WhatsApp have improved their relationship with friends Shabnam Shaikh et al.2019)⁴It has connecting people easier, faster and enhancing effective flow of message, sharing ideas among peers (Yeboah, Ewur 2014, Irfan and Dhimmarr2019)⁵. whatsAap makes virtual world, new friendship and improve communications among people (Shettigar and Karinagannanavar 2016)⁶. Youths are spending enormous time on social media for entertainment purpose whereas academic and career related purpose was lagging (Irfan and Dhimmarr2019)⁷. Issa Omar Malecela⁸ concluded that, as learning tool WhatsAap has beneficial to both students and instructors. Singhal and Chawla⁹ said that, WhatsApp and Facebook have positive impact in academic and professional lives of medical students and doctors. It has increasing collaborative learning and social interactivity with peers. Further they noted that whatsapp has negative impacts on youth and adversely affects their education, behaviour and routine lives. The excessive use of social networking sites for recreational purpose has negative impact on their mental and social health as well as it has reduced the users’ interpersonal interaction with family and friends. According to L. Cetinkaya¹⁰ the utility of whatsapp in education process as a supportive technology because in an education process learning environment is more important than whatsApp.

➤ Objective

- To understand the usage and impact of WhatsApp mobile application among the youths of rural Vaijapur.
- To identify the degree of positive and negative impacts of using WhatsApp
- To explore the impact of WhatsApp on individuals personal and social relations of the youth.

III. LITERATURE AND METHOD

A quantitative approach is used to conduct research, survey was conducted among randomly selected WhatsApp user in rural Vijapur with sample size of 310 students between the age group of 18 to 21 year students during July – August 2022. All graduate students willing to participate and give the consent for the study were included.

Table 1 Gender Wise Classification of Respondents

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	Male	150	48.38
2	Female	160	51.61
	Total	310	100.00

The table shows that out of 310 respondents 48.38% are boys and 51.61% were girls.

Table 2 Faculty Wise Distribution of Respondents

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	BA	89	28.70
2	B.SC	67	21.61
3	B.COM	126	40.64
4	PG	28	9.03
	Total	310	100.00

Source: Field Survey

The table shows that 90.97 % are undergraduate students (28.70 % from Arts, 21.61% from Science and 40.64% are from commerce faculty) while 9.03% of the respondents are postgraduates.

Table 3 Use of Social Media

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	Facebook	119	38.38
2	WhatsApp	283	91.29
3	Tutor	49	15.80
4	instagram	21	6.77
5	skypee	30	9.67
6	telegram	150	48.38
7	Blog	3	0.96
8	Other	61	19.67
	Total	310	100.00

Source: Field Survey

The chart above shows the social media usage patterns of respondents. A look at the charts shows that 38.38 % of children use Facebook. 91.29 % respondents use WhatsApp. 15.80 % .6.77% Instagram. 9.67% Skype, 48.38% children use Telegram channel. Observation of the above tables shows that 0.96 % use blogs and 19.67 % other children use social media.

Table 4 Daily use Patterns of WhatsApp

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	1 hours	59	19.03
2	1-2 hour	148	47.74
3	2-3 hours	44	14.19
4	More than 3 hours	59	19.03
	Total	310	100.00

Source: Field Survey

The chart above shows the social media usage time of a consumer. A look at the charts shows that 19.03% of the respondents say they use WhatsApp at least one hour daily. According to 47.74 % respondent they use WhatsApp regularly for 1-2 hours daily. 14.19 % respondents are using social media WhatsApp for 2-3 hours. Whereas 19.03% respondents say they use WhatsApp more than three hours daily.

Table 5 Using WhatsApp in Running Class

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	Yes	29	9.35
2	No	281	90.64
	Total	310	100.00

90.64% students say they don't check WhatsApp status while class is going on.

Table 6 WhatsApp Writing Languages

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	Marathi	54	17.41
2	Hindi	10	3.22
3	English	35	11.29
4	Marathi in English wording	211	68.06
	Total	310	100.00

When the students were asked about the language of writing messages on WhatsApp, the students have shown their response as follows. 68.06% of the students say that they write using English words from Marathi. 11.29% students say they write messages in English language. Among 17.41 % students they write message from Marathi language while only 3.22% students use Hindi language for message writing.

Table 7 Purpose of Whatsapp use

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	Easy to use	87	28.06
2	Useful for communication	103	33.22
3	As time and money savings	75	24.19
4	As the need of the hour	123	39.67
5	As a reputation	41	13.22
6	To spend time	44	14.19
7	To get information	224	72.25
	Total	310	100

When we asked the students why they are use WhatsApp or what the purposes of using WhatsApp, the students responded as follows. 72.25% students say they use WhatsApp for the purpose of getting information. 39.67% students say WhatsApp is the need of the hour so they feel it is important to use it. 14.19% of students say that they use WhatsApp to pass time. 13.22% of students indicate that they use it because of today's status or station. 24.19% of students say that the purpose of using WhatsApp is to save time and money. 30.22% students use WhatsApp as an important medium for messaging or communication while 28.06% students use WhatsApp because it is easy to use.

Table 8 Main Purpose of WhatsApp use?

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	Sending text messages	143	46.12
2	Sending photos	105	33.87
3	Video sharing	71	22.90
4	Video calling	76	24.51
5	Chanting with friends	136	43.87
6	Other	111	35.80
	Total	310	100

When trying to find out what the students use this medium for, the response received from the students is as follows. 46.12% percent of students say they use WhatsApp to send message test messages. According to 30.87 percent students use WhatsApp to send photos. 22.9% students say they share videos among their friends and relatives. 24.51% students say they use WhatsApp for video calling. 43.87% students say they use WhatsApp for chatting with friends and 35.80% students say they use WhatsApp for other reasons.

Table 9 Application of WhatsApp Message

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	Changes in habits	115	37.09
2	Acquire new skills	181	58.38
3	Archived favourite messages	79	25.48

4	Helped the needy financially	72	23.22
5	None of these	82	26.45
	Total	310	100.00

When students were asked if they have changed their behaviour because of a message received or read on WhatsApp, the students have shown the following responses. According to 37.09% of the students that message has changed the habits of the students. According to 58.38% students they have acquired new skills. Collected by 25.48% respondents say favourite message reading. 32.22% of the respondents say that they have helped the needy person. 26.45% of the students say that there is no change in their behaviour because of the message they read on WhatsApp.

Table 10 Nature of Information Sending on WhatsApp Groups

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	News	133	42.10
2	Jokes	76	24.51
3	quiz questions	50	16.12
4	Inspirational Quotes	78	25.16
5	Advertising	72	23.22
6	Educational information	202	65.16
7	Other	58	18.70
	Total	310	100.00

When he was asked about what information he sends through WhatsApp, he responded as follows. 42.10% respondents say they send news or news to others on WhatsApp. 24.51% respondents mentioned that they send jokes. 16.12% respondents said that they send information about a competition on WhatsApp. 25.16% of students said that they send motivational or inspirational lectures or information to others. 23.22% respondents said that they send advertisements in context. Send to others. 65.16% send educational information to others while 18.70% share other information with others through WhatsApp.

Table 11 Which of the following Actions do you do Every Day on WhatsApp?

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	Commenting on other people's messages	109	35.16
2	Changing states	79	25.48
3	Viewing the status of others	119	38.38
4	None of these / others	116	37.41
	Total	310	100.00

When the respondents were asked about how they do daily activities on WhatsApp, they gave the following response. 35.16% respondents say they react to messages sent by others. 25.48% respondents say they change their status daily. 38.38% of the respondents say that they check others' status or DP on WhatsApp while 37.41% of the respondents say that they do not do any of the above.

Table 12 Reaction to Respond to your Message

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	You view others' last seen updates	56	18.06
2	get angry	43	13.87
3	Constantly thinking the same thing	37	11.93
4	Asking why not answer	70	22.58
5	None of these.	170	54.83
	Total	310	100.00

Respondents have shown the following responses when asked how they might react if others do not respond to their messages. 18.06% respondents say they see the last scene update of the other person. 13.87% respondents say they feel angry with the other person. 11.93% of respondents say they constantly wonder why they didn't respond to your message. 22.58% of the respondents mentioned that they ask the other person why they did not respond to me while 54.83% of the respondents said that we do not do any of these actions.

Table 13 Impact of WhatsApp use on Respondents

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	Supplementary Practice for study	170	54.83
2	Adverse effects on the study	85	27.41
3	Waste of precious time	78	25.16

4	Enhancing general knowledge	121	39.03
5	Useful to develop professional skills	107	34.51
	Total	310	100.00

54. 83% of students say that WhatsApp is a supplement for studies when asked about the use or benefit of WhatsApp for students. 27. 41% respondents mention that it affects studies badly. 25.16 % respondents say WhatsApp is wasting valuable time. 39.03% respondents mention that WhatsApp has increased their knowledge. 34.51% respondents say WhatsApp has helped them develop professional skills.

Table 14 Impact of WhatsApp on Social Relation

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	Social relations have become stronger	187	60.32
2	Interference of others has increased in the private life.	83	26.77
3	Mental stress (isolation) has increased	84	27.09
4	Arising Social disputes	78	25.16
5	is a stress relieving medium	92	29.67
	Total	310	100.00

When trying to understand the impact of WhatsApp on the social relations of the students, the data shows that, 60.32 % of the respondents say that social relations have become closer because of WhatsApp. 26.77% respondents mentioned that WhatsApp has increased interference in social relationships. 27.09% of the respondents said that WhatsApp has increased mental stress. 25.16% of the respondents said that WhatsApp is causing social conflicts or problems. 29.67% respondents say WhatsApp reduces stress.

Table 15 Nature of WhatsApp Addiction

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	No	118	38.06
2	Yes	192	61.93
	Total	310	100.00

61.93% respondents say they are addicted to WhatsApp. While 38.6 percent respondents say no.

Table 16 Role of WhatsApp in Providing Knowledge of Global Events

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	Yes	270	87.09
2	No	40	12.90
	Total	310	100.00

87.09% of the respondents say that WhatsApp keeps them informed about world affairs.

Table 17 Nature of Message Checking on WhatsApp

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	No	134	43.22
2	Yes	176	56.77
	Total	310	100.00

56.77% of the respondents say that they check WhatsApp in their mobile phone right after waking up. 43.52 percent of the respondents say that they do not check WhatsApp on their mobile phone after waking up from sleep.

Table 18 Causes for Irritability?

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	Forgetting the phone	72	23.22
2	No mobile charging	100	32.25
3	Lack of internet pack	79	25.48
4	Mobile is not running	77	24.83
5	None of these	165	53.22
	Total	310	100.00

When trying to know if there is any relation between increased irritability among students and mobile, the respondent gave the following response that 23.22 % of the respondents say that after forgetting their phone at home, their irritability increases. 32.25% of the respondents say that their irritation increases if the mobile phone is not charging. 25.48% of the respondents say that their irritation increases if there is no internet in their mobile. 24.83 percent of the respondents say that they get irritated if their mobile phone is not charging. Whereas 53.22% respondents say that they do not feel any of the above types of irritability in their nature.

Table 19 Impact of Whatsapp on Behaviour

Sr. No.	Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
1	Addicted to mobile usage	102	32.90
2	Decreased book reading	190	61.29
3	Ignored outdoor play	123	39.67
4	The conversation with the man in the house decreased	119	38.38
5	Increased virtual speaking to people who are not nearby	101	32.58
6	Ignore TV and newspapers	153	49.35
	Total	310	100.00

When trying to know the changes in the life of students due to mobile, the following comes to hand: 32.90% respondents say that they are subjected or enslaved by mobile. 61.29% of the respondents say that the amount of book reading has decreased. 39.67 % respondents say that playing outdoor sports has decreased. 38.38 percent of the respondents say that the conversation with the person at home has decreased. 32.58% respondents say there is an increase in talking to virtual human. 49.35% of the respondents say that the amount of newspaper and TV viewing has decreased due to mobile phones.

IV. FINDINGS

Out of 310 the 283 (91.29) % respondents are using WhatsApp. 43. 87% students say they use WhatsApp for chatting with friends. 54. 83% of students say that WhatsApp is a supplement for studies. 39.03% respondents mention that WhatsApp has increased their knowledge. 60.32 % of the respondents say that social relations have become closer because of WhatsApp. 61.93% respondents say they are addicted by WhatsApp. 87.09% of the respondents say that WhatsApp keeps them informed about world affairs. 56.77% of the respondents say that they check WhatsApp in their mobile phone right after waking up. 61.29% of the respondents say that the amount of book reading has decreased. 49.35% of the respondents say that the amount of newspaper and TV viewing has decreased due to mobile phones.

V. CONCLUSION

When trying to understand the impact of WhatsApp on personality of college students, it is seen that students are spending more time on WhatsApp usage. They are more trusting in their relationship with virtually. Talking with family members, reading a book, watching TV has declined today due to the use of WhatsApp. There has also been an increase in reacting to others on WhatsApp, wondering why others didn't reply to the message you sent, and checking WhatsApp as soon as you wake up. Lack of charging of mobiles, forgetting of mobiles, lack of light and lack of recharge etc. have increased irritability among students. WhatsApp has increased interference in social relationships

and has led to depression among students. Most of the students have admitted that they are addicted to WhatsApp today. Therefore, in order to reduce the negative effects of WhatsApp or other social media on students, it is necessary to inform them and it is also necessary to create media literacy.

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